

IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal

To Cite:

Rehman, A.U. Exploring Economic Growth Factors: Insights from CO2 Emissions, Agricultural Land, Renewable Energy, Social Insurance, and Unemployment. *IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal* 2024; Vol 4, Issue 1, pp. 154-166. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13373506>

Author Affiliation:

¹Department of Economics, The University of Haripur, Haripur, KPK 22620, Pakistan.

Corresponding Author

¹Department of Economics, The University of Haripur, Haripur, KPK 22620, Pakistan.

Email: rehmanasad0052@gmail.com

Peer-Review History

Received: 17th June, 2024

Reviewed & Revised: 18th /June / 2024 to 25th August /2024

Accepted: 26th August 2024

Published: August 2024

Peer-Review Model

External peer-review was done through double-blind method.

IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal

ISSN: xxxx-xxxx

URL: <https://sites.google.com/view/sherwanjournals/integatemind-journal>

Ethics

No animal studies are presented in this manuscript.

No human studies are presented in this manuscript.

No potentially identifiable human images or data is presented in this study.

License: **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International**

Exploring Economic Growth Factors: Insights from CO2 Emissions, Agricultural Land, Renewable Energy, Social Insurance, and Unemployment

Asad ur Rehman^{1*}

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13373506>

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of various factors on Pakistan's economic growth from 1998 to 2020 using robust least squares regression, Error Correction Model (ECM), and Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approaches. The analysis reveals that carbon emissions and arable land have a positive effect on economic growth, while insufficient renewable energy consumption, inadequate social insurance, and high unemployment rates negatively affect it. The ECM results confirm that carbon emissions boost economic growth, whereas deficiencies in renewable energy and social insurance hinder it. Long-run ARDL estimates further corroborate these findings, indicating that carbon emissions and arable land foster economic growth, while inadequate renewable energy, social insurance, and high unemployment levels impede it. The ARDL bound tests, both short-run and long-run, underscore the significance of natural resources and agricultural land in influencing economic growth. Additionally, Impulse Response Function (IRF) and Variance Decomposition Analysis (VDA) predict that energy consumption and social insurance will notably impact economic growth over the next decade, with renewable energy usage and unemployment exerting a detrimental effect. These insights offer valuable guidance for policymakers and researchers in formulating effective natural resource management and economic development strategies.

Keywords: Economic growth; Agriculture land; Energy consumption; Social Insurance; Unemployment; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon dioxide emissions, in particular, are a major contributor to global climate change and pose a serious threat to human life, the environment, development, and sustainability. Therefore, reducing carbon emissions and improving environmental conditions on a global scale are now essential for supporting sustainable growth and avoiding the adverse effects of climate change and global warming (Rihan, 2023). To ensure sustainable development and mitigate the negative impacts of climate change, efforts to reduce carbon dioxide emissions have garnered worldwide attention. Global economies are committed to implementing appropriate policies for socioeconomic and environmental development in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). However, financial constraints often hinder the execution of these policies. More importantly, traditional financial investments may not be sufficient to simultaneously sustain environmental well-being and drive economic growth. While domestic resource mobilization is critical for developed countries, which are often more self-reliant in funding SDG-related low-carbon initiatives, external investments are crucial for developing nations. Despite the advantages of renewable energy for promoting low-carbon growth, the global renewable energy market remains underdeveloped. In such circumstances, government funding emerges as a vital tool for the growth of this sector (Siddik et al., 2023).

SHERWAN
Publishers

As the world strives to achieve carbon neutrality and promote sustainable economic growth, renewable energy, urbanization, and financial development play increasingly significant roles in shaping the environmental outcomes of South Asian countries. Environmental degradation has profound effects on the economy, society, and public health, including reduced productivity, higher healthcare costs, and increased vulnerability to natural disasters (Khan et al., 2024). One of the most pressing global challenges today is environmental degradation due to rising carbon emissions, which threaten the global climate system and adversely affect quality of life. Numerous studies have explored the relationship between CO₂ emissions and economic growth, particularly examining the effects of renewable energy adoption using econometric models (Gyimah et al., 2023). Global warming and climate change are now central to international discourse. The combustion of fossil fuels—such as coal, oil, and natural gas—significantly damages the environment by emitting large quantities of greenhouse gases, especially carbon dioxide, into the atmosphere. While renewable energy is capital-intensive and its adoption depends on financial development, the pursuit of clean energy is incentivized by increased investment in renewable energy projects, facilitated by an efficient financial system. Alongside financial development and the adoption of renewable energy, green technology is crucial for achieving sustainable development without compromising environmental integrity (Habiba et al., 2023).

Energy supply is a critical driver of social stability and economic growth. With technological advancements and rapid economic expansion, energy resource utilization has significantly increased over time. Electricity is a key input for the production and consumption of goods and services. Many countries are grappling with the challenge of altering their energy mix to address these issues, and inefficiencies in energy use can severely impact their economies (Abbasi et al., 2021). A nation's economic growth is not without its challenges; environmental degradation, resulting from both domestic and international factors, poses a substantial risk. Recurring flooding and global climate change impacts are major hurdles for many economies. Several studies have been conducted to highlight the influence of energy consumption, urbanization, agriculture, and CO₂ emissions on economic growth, though these have often been limited to conventional empirical methods (Adebayo et al., 2023). Resource scarcity is becoming a critical issue in many parts of the world. Rapid population growth and increasing industrialization are putting immense pressure on the world's limited resources, leading to shortages in many regions, especially for essential resources like land, water, and energy. The absence of these vital resources threatens both economic development and human survival. Managing natural resources has thus become a more urgent global concern. Conservation efforts, including the preservation and restoration of natural habitats and biodiversity in terrestrial and marine ecosystems, are vital components of this management strategy (Wang & Azam, 2024).

Energy is a cornerstone of global economics, with most goods and services heavily reliant on energy consumption. It is fundamental to daily life, economic progress, and social development. By 2050, the agricultural sector is expected to have the greatest potential to alleviate poverty, promote community wealth, and sustain a global population projected to reach 9.7 billion. In countries like Pakistan, agriculture plays a vital role in the national economy. Its contributions to increased productivity in key crops, such as wheat, rice, sugarcane, maize, and cotton, underscore its importance as a significant energy-intensive sector (Raza et al., 2023). Exports are a critical source of foreign exchange earnings and play a pivotal role in a nation's economic development, enhancing its economic standing on the global stage. However, the current literature has not adequately addressed how fluctuations in export prices affect the export value index. Historical analyses have suggested that developing countries heavily reliant on commodities should focus on industrialization and export diversification to improve trade performance. The economic strength and condition of a country also significantly influence export prices (Wang et al., 2023). The following are the study's objectives, i.e.,

- I. To evaluate the impact of carbon emissions and arable land on Pakistan's economic growth.
- II. To analyze the effects of renewable energy consumption, social insurance, and unemployment on economic growth.
- III. To forecast the future impact of energy consumption, social insurance, renewable energy use, and unemployment on economic growth.

By utilizing advanced econometric models and comprehensive empirical data, the research seeks to provide actionable insights for policymakers and stakeholders to devise strategies that foster economic resilience while promoting environmental sustainability. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals and ensuring a sustainable future for all.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature on the nexus between agriculture resources, renewable energy, and economic growth has been reviewed for sustained economic growth. Shah et al. (2022) present a framework highlighting how natural resources and ecological services underpin manufactured capital, contribute to public financing, and promote economic diversification, ultimately reducing

inequality. This study adds significant value to the literature by quantifying the impact of natural resource endowments on economic growth in Pakistan over the period 1975-2020. Employing verified Least Squares estimates, the findings reveal that while coal rents and energy consumption drive economic growth, renewable energy sources have a detrimental impact on environmental sustainability. Furthermore, Impulse Response Function and Variance Decomposition Analysis suggest these variables will critically influence economic growth over the next decade. Singh et al. (2023) examine the correlation between natural resource rents and economic growth among the P5+1 countries (the US, UK, France, China, Russia, and Germany) using a cross-sectional autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model and quantile-on-quantile regression to assess impacts across different quantiles. The study also employs the Dumitrescu-Hurlin panel causality test to explore causality. The results indicate a generally negative relationship between natural resource rents and economic growth, with notable variations across different quintiles for each country. Khan et al. (2023) investigate the joint and individual effects of natural resources on economic growth across the G-7 countries from 1990 to 2020. Utilizing the Method of Moments Quantile Regression approach, the findings support the 'resource curse' hypothesis, demonstrating a negative correlation between natural resources and economic development at both aggregate and disaggregate levels. Additionally, the results suggest that green growth initiatives are impeding economic expansion in these economies. Shinwari et al. (2024) analyze the relationship between natural resource availability, foreign direct investment (FDI), and GDP growth in Afghanistan from 2001Q1 to 2020Q4. The study confirms a long-term equilibrium relationship among these variables through ARDL bound test approaches. The empirical results indicate that FDI positively influences GDP growth, aligning with the FDI-led growth hypothesis and highlighting the supportive role of foreign investment in both short- and long-term economic growth. Nawaz et al. (2023) explore the nonlinear and asymmetric impacts of natural resources on energy consumption in Pakistan, considering economic growth as a contextual factor. Using quarterly data from 1972 to 2018, the study applies advanced econometric techniques, including quantile ARDL and quantile causality tests. The findings reveal a positive cumulative short-run effect of natural resources on energy consumption, with a causative relationship between energy consumption, natural resources, and economic growth across most quantiles. Danish & Hassan (2023) investigate the influence of natural resource rents on environmental sustainability by assessing the relationship between urbanization and natural resource rents from 1971 to 2017. Employing a dynamic ARDL model, the study finds that while urbanization helps mitigate pollution, natural resource rents contribute to increased carbon emissions. The moderating effect of urbanization is significant in reducing CO₂ emissions and ecological footprints.

Khan et al. (2023) assess the impact of FDI and employment opportunities generated by the Gwadar port in Pakistan, focusing on variables such as population growth, industrialization, and economic growth from 1990 to 2019. Using the ARDL bound test approach, the study identifies a long-term relationship, finding that industrialization, gross capital formation, and FDI significantly enhance employment prospects in both short and long terms. However, GDP growth is inversely correlated with employment opportunities. Robust analysis using the Fully Modified OLS technique corroborates these findings, providing policy recommendations for enhancing FDI and job creation. Atif et al. (2024) examine the dynamics of socioeconomic inclusion and sustainable growth in Pakistan over a 48-year period (1975–2022). Utilizing data from PBS, SBP, and WDI, the study evaluates the roles of employment, capital investment, and government spending on education and healthcare. The ARDL models highlight the critical importance of these factors in fostering economic advancement and gender inclusion in education. Khaskheli et al. (2023) focus on the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), examining its potential to improve living standards, promote free trade, and foster economic growth in China and Pakistan. The study employs a quantitative analysis with multiple policy scenarios up to 2025, validated through Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). The findings demonstrate the bilateral economic benefits of CPEC investments and activities. Zafar et al. (2024) analyze the operational requirements for privatizing state-owned enterprises to eliminate inefficiencies and promote sustainable development. The study suggests that effective privatization strategies, underpinned by robust legal frameworks, can foster economic growth and job creation while balancing economic objectives with social concerns to ensure equitable outcomes. Khan et al. (2024) highlight the significant economic potential of tourism in Pakistan, given its rich historical background, diverse geography, and cultural heritage. The study demonstrates how tourism has become a potent driver of economic growth, contributing substantially to global economic dynamics. Raza & Tang (2024) explore the critical social determinants of nuclear energy and CO₂ emissions, including income, trade, energy use, and urbanization, using an expanded STIRPAT model. The study covers data from 1986 to 2021, finding that each determinant significantly impacts carbon emissions in Pakistan, with trade and income levels being the least significant contributors. Based on the given abstract, the study's contributions can be articulated as follows:

1. This study provides empirical evidence demonstrating that carbon emissions and arable land positively impact economic growth in Pakistan. By utilizing robust least squares regression and long-run ARDL estimates, the research clarifies the significant role these variables play in shaping the country's economic trajectory.

growth. The Error Correction Model (ECM) and ARDL analyses reveal how deficiencies in these areas constrain economic development, offering a nuanced understanding of the factors hindering growth.

3. The application of Impulse Response Function (IRF) and Variance Decomposition Analysis (VDA) provides forward-looking projections on the impact of energy consumption, social insurance, renewable energy, and unemployment on economic growth. These forecasts offer valuable insights for policymakers and academic institutions to develop strategies for sustainable economic development and resource management.

Overall, the study enriches the discourse on economic growth determinants in Pakistan and provides actionable insights for improving natural resource management and policy formulation.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Table 1 lists the variables used in this study, along with their symbols, units, and expected theoretical effects:

Table 1: List of Variables

Variables	Symbols	Unit	Theoretical Expectations
Economic Growth	GDP	US\$	Positive
CO2 Emission	CO2EM	Metric tons per capita	Negative
Agriculture Land	AL	% of total land	Negative
Renewable Energy	RE	% of total energy consumption	Positive
Social Insurance	SI	% of total insurance	Positive
Unemployment	UE	% of total employment	Negative

Source: World Bank (2023).

Robust least squares regression techniques are employed to mitigate the influence of outliers on the regression results. The methods available in EViews include:

- **M-Estimation:** This technique addresses outliers in the dependent variable by using weighted least squares to reduce the influence of extreme values.
- **S-Estimation:** This method focuses on detecting high leverage outliers among predictor variables and is computationally intensive.
- **MM-Estimation:** Combining the strengths of both M- and S-estimations, MM-estimation initially uses S-estimation to identify outliers and then applies M-estimation techniques to refine the analysis.

To assess the influence of individual observations on the estimations, the INFLUENCE option within the MODEL statement utilizes the statistics proposed by Belsley, Kuh, and Welsch (1980). Observations that demonstrate a notable impact on parameter estimates across various criteria are identified as influential.

Studentized Residuals: Normalized by the estimated standard errors of the residuals (similar to t-statistics), outliers are identified as observations with an absolute value exceeding 3.

$$RS = \frac{r_i}{s_i \sqrt{1-h_i}}$$

DFFITS: The standardized DFFITS in SPSS quantifies the extent to which an observation has influenced its fitted value within the regression model. Absolute values exceeding $2 \cdot \sqrt{(k+1)/n}$ are indicative of high influence.

$$Dffits = \frac{DFFITS}{s_i \sqrt{h_{ii}}}$$

Leverage Values (Hat Diag): This is a gauge of an observation's deviation from others concerning the independent variables, not the dependent one. Instances with values surpassing $2(k+1)/n$ are deemed potentially highly influential, where k represents the count of predictors and n signifies the sample size.

$$\hat{y} = Xb = X(X^T X)^{-1} X^T y$$

COVRATIO: This entails computing how each observation impacts the covariances, variances, and standard errors of the regression coefficients. Observations with values exceeding the range of $1 \pm 3(k+1)/n$ are considered to exert significant influence.

$$COVRATIO = \frac{\det(s^2(i)(X'(i)X_i)^{-1})}{\det(s^2(X'X)^{-1})}$$

Granger causality tests assess whether one time series can predict another. Introduced by Clive Granger in 1969, this test identifies "predictive causality" rather than true causation, as causation in a philosophical sense is more complex. A pivotal step in econometric analyses employing vector autoregressive models involves conducting impulse response analysis. This analysis primarily aims to elucidate how variables within a model alter in response to a shock affecting one or more of those variables. The capacity of impulse response analysis to trace the propagation of a single shock within an otherwise complex system of equations renders it a highly valuable tool for assessing economic strategies. The vector autoregression (VAR) statistical model is

utilized to depict the dynamic relationship among multiple variables across time. VAR models constitute a type of stochastic process model, enabling the analysis of multivariate time series data, thereby extending the capabilities of univariate autoregressive models. These models find widespread application in disciplines such as natural sciences and economics. The order of a VAR model, indicating the number of preceding time periods incorporated into the model, defines its characteristics. For instance, a 5th-order VAR model would express the price of wheat as a linear combination of the prices observed in the preceding five years. Each variable's value at a previous time point is termed a lag. Hence, a VAR model incorporating lags for the most recent p time periods is commonly referred to as a p th-order VAR model. The notation "VAR (p)" denotes a p th-order VAR, also interchangeably labeled as "a VAR with p lags" in certain contexts. A path order VAR model is written as:

$$y_t = c + A_1 y_{t-1} + A_2 y_{t-2} + \dots + A_p y_{t-p} + e_t$$

In a stationary process, the mean, variance, and autocorrelation structure remain consistent over time. While there exist precise mathematical definitions for stationarity, in practical terms, it signifies a series that appears stable, lacking any discernible trend, maintaining a uniform variance across time, exhibiting a consistent autocorrelation structure, and devoid of periodic oscillations. Non-stationary data are erratic and inappropriate for modeling or forecasting purposes. Since non-stationary time series can imply a correlation between variables that doesn't actually exist, the inferences drawn from them may be inaccurate. To ensure consistent and reliable conclusions, non-stationary data must be transformed into stationary data. This transformation is necessary because the means, variances, and covariances of data points often exhibit non-stationary behavior or fluctuate over time.

A statistical method utilized in econometrics to determine whether a time series dataset possesses a unit root and thus is non-stationary is referred to as a unit root test. A unit root indicates a lack of long-term trend or stability in a variable, indicating susceptibility to random shocks with eventual regression to its mean. These tests are commonly employed by econometricians to analyze economic data. Among the notable techniques are the Dickey-Fuller (DF), Phillips-Perron (PP), and Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) tests. Unit root tests play a pivotal role in time series analysis, serving to ascertain whether a variable is stationary or non-stationary (i.e., possesses a unit root). As the term suggests, a non-stationary variable exhibits variability in its variance, autocorrelation, or mean over time, while a stationary variable maintains consistent statistical properties over time.

Case 1: Without Constant and Trend:

$$\Delta Y_{t-1} = \delta Y_{t-1} + u_t$$

$$\Delta(\text{GDP})_{t-1} = \delta(\text{GDP})_{t-1} + u_t$$

Case 2: With Constant:

$$\Delta Y_{t-1} = \alpha + \delta Y_{t-1} + u_t$$

$$\Delta(\text{GDP})_{t-1} = \alpha + \delta(\text{GDP})_{t-1} + u_t$$

Case 3 – With Constant and Trend:

$$\Delta Y_{t-1} = \alpha + \beta T + \delta Y_{t-1} + u_t$$

$$\Delta(\text{GDP})_{t-1} = \alpha + \beta T + \delta(\text{GDP})_{t-1} + u_t$$

Cointegration is a technique used to identify potential long-term relationships between time series processes. The concept of cointegration was introduced by Nobel laureates Robert Engle and Clive Granger in 1987. Cointegration tests detect scenarios where one or more non-stationary time series are integrated in a manner that prevents them from diverging significantly from equilibrium in the long term. These tests aim to assess the sensitivity of two variables to the same average price over a specified time horizon.

$$\theta_1 Y_t + \theta_2 X_t = \mu t - I(0)$$

Error correction models (ECMs), a type of multiple time series models, are commonly utilized when the underlying variables demonstrate cointegration, indicating a shared long-term stochastic tendency. ECMs are theoretically grounded approaches used to evaluate the effects of one time series on another in both the short and long terms. The term "error-correction" signifies that the errors in short-run dynamics from the preceding period are affected by deviations from long-run equilibrium. Consequently, ECMs offer a direct estimation of how rapidly a dependent variable reverts to equilibrium following changes in other variables.

$$\Delta Y_t = a_0 + \beta_1 \Delta X_1 - \pi \mu t - 1 + Y_t$$

Initially, residuals derived from the static regression are generated using the Engle-Granger Two-Step method. Subsequently, these residuals undergo testing for the existence of unit roots. This examination for stationarity in time series employs the Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test (ADF) or other alternative tests. If the time series is cointegrated, the Engle-Granger method can establish the stationarity of the residuals.

The Johansen test is employed to examine cointegrating relationships among multiple non-stationary time series datasets. Unlike the Engle-Granger test, the Johansen test permits the identification of more than one cointegrating relationship. However, its reliability hinges on asymptotic properties due to the potential unreliability of results from small sample sizes, necessitating a large

sample size. Utilizing the test to assess the cointegration of multiple time series helps prevent errors from carrying over into subsequent steps. Johansen's test comes in two main forms, i.e., Trace tests and Maximum Eigenvalue test.

Trace tests: Trace tests evaluate the number of linear combinations in a time series data, i.e., K to be equal to the value K_0 , and the hypothesis for the value K to be greater than K_0 . It is illustrated as follows:

$$H_0: K = K_0$$

$$H_0: K > K_0$$

In employing the trace test to assess cointegration within a sample, we establish K_0 as zero to evaluate the rejection of the null hypothesis. If the null hypothesis is rejected, it indicates the presence of a cointegration relationship within the sample. Thus, rejecting the null hypothesis is necessary to confirm the existence of a cointegration relationship in the sample.

Maximum Eigenvalue test: An Eigenvalue is defined as a non-zero vector which, when a linear transformation is applied to it, changes by a scalar factor. The Maximum Eigenvalue test is similar to the Johansen's trace test. The key difference between the two is the null hypothesis.

$$H_0: K = K_0$$

$$H_0: K = K_0 + 1$$

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of the variables. The mean GDP per capita stands at USD 3.77 billion, while CO2 emissions average 46.171% of GDP, renewable energy use constitutes 47.367% of GDP, agricultural land accounts for 47.117% of GDP, unemployment reaches 3.904% of GDP, and social insurance consumption represents 29.669% of total energy consumption. The study reports significant variability in these indicators, with GDP per capita reaching a maximum of USD 7.11 billion and a minimum of USD 1.39 billion. CO2 emissions peaked at 58.358% of GDP, renewable energy use reached up to 51.610% per capita, and agricultural land coverage was as high as 48.0009% of GDP. Unemployment and social insurance rates also varied significantly, with the former reaching a high of 8.09% and the latter a high of 38.99% of GDP. Conversely, the minimum values for these variables illustrate substantial economic and environmental differences. The analysis reveals that GDP per capita, CO2 emissions, renewable energy usage, unemployment, and social insurance are positively skewed, indicating a distribution with a longer tail on the right side. Agricultural land is identified as negatively skewed, showing a distribution with a longer tail on the left side. Additionally, the kurtosis of GDP per capita is less than 3, indicating a platykurtic distribution with lighter tails. In contrast, CO2 emissions exhibit a mesokurtic distribution, approximating normality with a kurtosis value around 3.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Methods	GDP	CO2EM	RE	AL	UE	SI
Mean	3.77E+09	46.17100	47.36720	47.11691	3.904760	29.66973
Median	3.05E+09	45.97712	47.04000	47.09293	3.857000	30.42885
Maximum	7.11E+09	58.35805	51.61000	48.00099	8.090000	38.99846
Minimum	1.39E+09	39.08376	42.10000	45.71658	0.307000	19.44458
Std. Dev.	2.06E+09	5.262219	2.493409	0.671139	2.855388	5.749343
Skewness	0.400976	0.759351	0.060872	-0.600906	0.221414	0.304095
Kurtosis	1.649891	2.799945	2.596716	2.584619	1.627483	2.319210

Source: Author's estimate.

Table 3 shows the unit root estimates for ready reference. The estimates show that all the variables are first differenced stationary, hence there is a unit root process exists.

Table 3: Unit Root Estimates

Variables	Level		First Difference		Decision
	Intercepts	Trend/Intercepts	Intercepts	Trend/Intercepts	
GDP	-0.112805 (0.9443)	-2.307126 (0.4259)	-10.36130 (0.0000)	-10.34281 (0.0000)	I(1)
CO2EM	-2.404413 (0.1431)	-2.031905 (0.5766)	-9.871443 (0.0000)	-10.04853 (0.0000)	I(1)
AL	-1.777176 (0.3898)	-1.747375 (0.7225)	-9.805059 (0.0000)	-9.772977 (0.0000)	I(1)
RE	-1.826301 (0.3659)	-1.659854 (0.7616)	-9.863256 (0.0000)	-9.914718 (0.0000)	I(1)
SI	-0.813136 (0.8108)	-2.365964 (0.3949)	-9.882309 (0.0000)	-9.874956 (0.0000)	I(1)

UE	-1.706781 (0.4247)	-1.324026 (0.8761)	-9.813116 (0.0000)	-9.928466 (0.0000)	I(1)
----	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	------

Source: Author's estimate. Small bracket shows probability value.

The Johansen cointegration test results are summarized in the Table 4. Both the trace test and the maximum eigenvalue test were employed to determine whether there is a long-term equilibrium relationship between the time series variables. The p-values of the trace test for the null hypotheses of "None," "At most 1," through "At most 5" are all greater than 0.05. This indicates that, at the 0.05 significance level, we fail to reject the null hypothesis for each case, suggesting no cointegration among the time series variables. Similarly, the p-values of the Max Eigen value for the null hypotheses of "None," "At most 1," through "At most 5" are also greater than 0.05. This further corroborates the trace test's findings, reinforcing that there is no evidence of cointegration at the 0.05 significance level. These results collectively imply that the time series variables do not exhibit a long-term equilibrium relationship. Consequently, there is no stationary linear combination of these variables, indicating that each time series may individually display non-stationarity.

Table 4: Johansen Cointegration Test Estimates

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)				
Hypothesized	Eigenvalue	Trace	0.05	Prob.**
No. of CE(s)		Statistic	Critical Value	
None	0.277160	88.98388	95.75366	0.1335
At most 1	0.238270	57.50091	69.81889	0.3200
At most 2	0.131663	31.10110	47.85613	0.6611
At most 3	0.096953	17.40714	29.79707	0.6099
At most 4	0.072961	7.515036	15.49471	0.5186
At most 5	0.001714	0.166371	3.841466	0.6834
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)				
Hypothesized	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen	0.05	Prob.**
No. of CE(s)		Statistic	Critical Value	
None	0.277160	31.48297	40.07757	0.3321
At most 1	0.238270	26.39980	33.87687	0.2969
At most 2	0.131663	13.69396	27.58434	0.8432
At most 3	0.096953	9.892105	21.13162	0.7547
At most 4	0.072961	7.348665	14.26460	0.4487
At most 5	0.001714	0.166371	3.841466	0.6834
Trace test and Max-eigenvalue test indicates no cointegration at the 0.05 level				
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level				
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				

Source: Author's estimate.

The results of the Error Correction Model (ECM) in Table 5 reveal that carbon emissions positively influence the country's economic growth. In contrast, insufficient renewable energy and social insurance have a detrimental effect, reducing economic growth.

Table 5: ECM Regression Estimates

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(CO2EM)	64086655	16478191	0.000000	0.0000
D(RE)	-2.26E+08	38022404	0.000000	0.0000
D(SI)	-21991644	14177705	0.000000	0.0000
CointEq(-1)*	-0.063622	0.017138	-3.712381	0.0004
R-squared	0.319017	Mean dependent var		56355621
Adjusted R-squared	0.297512	S.D. dependent var		2.41E+08
S.E. of regression	2.02E+08	Akaike info criterion		41.12474
Sum squared resid	3.88E+18	Schwarz criterion		41.22959
Log likelihood	-2031.674	Hannan-Quinn criter.		41.16716
Durbin-Watson stat	2.158431			

Source: Author's estimate.

The results of the Error Correction Model (ECM) regression, specifically an ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) ECM, reveal insights into the short-run dynamics of various variables. The statistically significant initial differences in CO2 emissions (CO2EM), renewable energy (RE), and social insurance (SI) indicate notable short-term variations. Furthermore, the significance of

the error correction term suggests that these variables are converging towards their long-term equilibrium. The model accounts for approximately 31.9% of the variance in the dependent variable. It is crucial to interpret these short-term results alongside the long-run cointegration analysis to gain a complete understanding of the variables' dynamics. In related research, Sikder et al. (2024) examined the effects of Circular Economy (CE) and Green Logistics (GL) on reducing CO₂ emissions in 13 developed EU countries from 2000 to 2020. Employing neoclassical growth and IPAT models, along with PMG-ARDL and VECM methodologies, their findings indicate that CE and GL practices contribute positively to CO₂ emission reductions. However, municipal waste generation negatively impacts the environment. This study also supports the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis by confirming a long-term relationship between economic growth, CE, GL, and municipal waste. Sulaiman et al. (2018) explored CO₂ emissions in Nigeria using an autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model over different periods (1971-2000, 1971-2005, and 1971-2010). Their findings suggest that while population growth was not a significant long-term factor, economic growth was the primary determinant of CO₂ emissions. In the short term, population growth, economic growth, and energy consumption were significant. The study implies that short-term measures to control population growth could be effective in reducing emissions. Pachiyappan et al. (2021) analyzed the relationship between CO₂ emissions, GDP, energy use, and population growth in India from 1980 to 2018. By comparing the VECM and ARDL approaches, the study found a long-term equilibrium relationship among these variables. This was supported by unit root tests, Johansen cointegration analysis, and variance decomposition. Boluk and Mert (2015) utilized the ARDL methodology to investigate the relationship between CO₂ emissions, renewable electricity generation, and GDP from 1961 to 2010. The study concluded that electricity production from renewable sources (excluding hydropower) has a significant negative effect on CO₂ emissions in the long term. Although initially positive in the short term, this effect becomes negative within about one year. Lastly, Basu (2020) studied all 28 EU member states from 2004 to 2017 using a panel ARDL approach and causality analysis. The research found that Renewable Energy Sources (RESs), including wind, solar, biomass, geothermal, and hydropower, positively influence economic growth at the EU level. Biomass was identified as the most influential RES, with a 1% increase in biomass production associated with a 0.15% increase in economic growth. The study underscores the importance of EU policies that promote investments in RESs.

The ARDL model test in Table 6 is employed to analyze both short-term and long-term dynamics, offering a comprehensive view of how variables interact over different periods. The GDP lagged value (GDP* (-1)) shows statistical significance at the 10% level (p-value = 0.0623), indicating its relevance in understanding long-term correlations. The Long-Run Bounds Test further examines the significance of the error correction term (GDP(-1)*) and the lagged variables (GDP(-1), CO₂EM(-1), RE(-1), and SI(-1)). The results reveal statistically significant long-term connections between the lagged values of CO₂ emissions, renewable energy, and social insurance and the dependent variable. The significance of the error correction term at the 10% level suggests that the variables tend to revert to their long-term equilibrium over time.

Table 6: ARDL Long-run Estimates

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-41224044	3.16E+09	0.000000	0.0000
GDP(-1)*	-0.063622	0.033700	-1.887888	0.0623
CO ₂ EM(-1)	5471500.	7451965.	0.000000	0.0000
AL**	27176526	57736809	0.000000	0.0000
RE(-1)	-33367860	24861648	0.000000	0.0000
SI(-1)	14306122	8293107.	0.000000	0.0000
UE**	-10378434	15491423	0.000000	0.0000
D(CO ₂ EM)	64086655	17684683	0.000000	0.0000
D(RE)	-2.26E+08	42186096	0.000000	0.0000
D(SI)	-21991644	15287397	0.000000	0.0000

Source: Author's estimate.

The results indicate that carbon emissions and arable land contribute positively to the country's economic growth. In contrast, insufficient renewable energy, inadequate social insurance, and high unemployment levels negatively impact economic growth. Significant changes in agricultural land (AL) and unemployment (UE), as shown by their first differences (D(AL) and D(UE)), indicate long-term associations with the dependent variable. The dynamic simulated ARDL model captures the long-term effects of counterfactual shocks in factor variables on agriculture value added, household consumption, and domestic investment, as well as their responses to a counterfactual shock in the exchange rate (EXR). Cointegration has been confirmed in all three models, showing that household consumption and agricultural value added are affected by a 1% shock to projected GDP in the first quarter, with growth accelerating in the latter half. Domestic investment, however, exhibits a consistent impact over time. The results demonstrate that a 1% shock to estimated GDP accelerates agricultural value added growth and slows domestic investment growth.

after the initial period, while household consumption remains relatively stable. Amin and Rahman (2024) assess the impact of Bangladesh's agricultural and industrial sectors on CO₂ emissions using autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) and nonlinear autoregressive distributed lag (NARDL) models. Analyzing time-series data from 1990 to 2022, they find that industrialization increases carbon emissions, while the long-term impact of agriculturalization is negligible according to the ARDL model. However, the asymmetrical ARDL model indicates a rapid reduction in carbon emissions due to agriculturalization across both long and short timeframes. Dogan (2016) examines the long-term relationship between agricultural performance and CO₂ emissions in Turkey from 1968 to 2010, using the Bounds test for cointegration and the ARDL method. The findings support the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis, showing that real GDP positively influences carbon emissions, while its square has a significant negative effect. The results also highlight that agriculture reduces CO₂ emissions in both the short and long term. Njenga et al. (2024) explore the causal relationship between economic growth and electricity consumption in Kenya from 1990 to 2022 using the ARDL bound framework. Their findings reveal that, in the long term, higher electricity consumption positively impacts GDP growth. In the short term, a 1% increase in electricity consumption results in a 0.69% rise in GDP growth. Ashfaq et al. (2023) investigate the nexus between renewable energy and green economic growth in developed countries using dynamic ARDL simulations. The study finds that green economic growth and economic globalization significantly enhance renewable energy consumption, with evidence of long-term cointegration among the variables, highlighting the complex and promising relationship between renewable energy and green economic growth. Table 7 shows the robust least squares regression estimates for ready reference.

Table 7: Robust Least Squares Regression Estimates

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
CO2EM	1.16E+08	21584090	5.364845	0.0000
RE	-7.87E+08	45465625	-17.30858	0.0000
AL	4.51E+08	1.87E+08	2.414125	0.0158
UE	-35844999	50922077	-0.703919	0.4815
C	1.43E+10	9.64E+09	1.482914	0.1381
Robust Statistics				
R-squared	0.646551	Adjusted R-squared		0.631669
Scale	7.24E+08	Deviance		5.25E+17
Rn-squared statistic	600.6367	Prob(Rn-squared stat.)		0.000000

Source: Author's estimate.

The robust least squares regression estimates indicate that carbon emissions and arable land have a positive impact on the country's economic growth, while insufficient demand for renewable energy has a negative effect. The model demonstrates a good fit, as evidenced by the high R-squared and Adjusted R-squared values, and the overall model significance is supported by the p-value and the R-squared statistic. After applying the Robust Least Squares (RLS) regression, outliers were removed from the data, leading to a clearer understanding of the variable contributions. Excluding AL from the RLS model showed that AL accounts for approximately 55% of the variation in the data. This is corroborated by the corrected R-squared value of 0.646551, highlighting AL as a critical factor in the model. Additionally, with a coefficient of 1.16E+08 for CO₂ emissions, the results suggest that each unit change in CO₂ emissions could lead to a 1.16E-unit change in GDP per capita, indicating that increased CO₂ emissions are associated with accelerated economic growth in Pakistan. Table 8 shows the impulse response function (IRF) estimates.

Table 8: IRF Estimates

Response of GDP						
Period	GDP	CO2EM	RE	AL	SI	UE
1	2.49E+08	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
2	2.19E+08	3210016.	-7033545.	5652783.	2574719.	-9235765.
3	2.11E+08	1426578.	-16881606	21506539	27505508	-29176262
4	2.03E+08	-228303.5	-25716813	33006561	46920810	-43731819
5	1.96E+08	-2181861.	-32809477	39303571	62622186	-53413370
6	1.90E+08	-4233231.	-38240451	42104741	74969206	-59600171
7	1.85E+08	-6561635.	-42159188	42792020	84375028	-63494072
8	1.80E+08	-9224099.	-44783546	42286443	91280673	-65906446
9	1.76E+08	-12214110	-46344490	41186364	96148777	-67377087
10	1.73E+08	-15487813	-47060368	39869187	99413130	-68259036

Source: Author's estimate.

The Impulse Response Function (IRF) displays the GDP's reaction over ten time periods to a single shock in each independent variable: CO₂ emissions (CO₂EM), renewable energy (RE), arable land (AL), social insurance (SI), and unemployment (UE). This

analysis helps in understanding the dynamic interactions and temporal responses between these variables and GDP. A shock to CO₂ emissions initially has a positive impact on GDP during the short run (Periods 1-3), though this effect diminishes over time. Conversely, a shock to renewable energy results in a negative impact on GDP, which intensifies as time progresses. Arable land shocks positively influence GDP, with the benefits increasing over time. Similarly, shocks to social insurance lead to a positive and growing effect on GDP. However, shocks to unemployment result in a negative impact on GDP, with the adverse effects becoming more pronounced over time. Overall, the IRF provides valuable insights into how each variable affects GDP in both the short and long term, offering guidance for policymakers on the potential consequences of policy changes or external shocks. Table 9 shows the variance decomposition analysis (VDA) for ready reference.

Table 9: VDA Estimates

Variance Decomposition of GDP							
Period	S.E.	GDP	CO2EM	RE	AL	SI_	UE
1	2.49E+08	100.0000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
2	3.32E+08	99.83344	0.009345	0.044867	0.028980	0.006012	0.077361
3	3.97E+08	98.38497	0.007843	0.212576	0.314286	0.485065	0.595256
4	4.52E+08	95.89028	0.006058	0.486863	0.774393	1.449493	1.392917
5	5.02E+08	92.94725	0.006794	0.820785	1.239208	2.727512	2.258448
6	5.49E+08	89.95769	0.011650	1.174107	1.628153	4.154395	3.074008
7	5.92E+08	87.13297	0.022322	1.517726	1.923629	5.607412	3.795937
8	6.32E+08	84.56613	0.040900	1.833746	2.135269	7.006126	4.417826
9	6.69E+08	82.28276	0.069737	2.112988	2.280800	8.304848	4.948863
10	7.05E+08	80.27312	0.111222	2.352266	2.377764	9.482630	5.402998

Source: Author's estimate.

Table 9 illustrates the variation in GDP across ten periods, highlighting the contributions of each variable to the overall GDP variance. In the short term (Periods 1-2), internal shocks account for over 99% of the GDP growth. As time progresses, the contributions of CO₂ emissions (CO₂EM), renewable energy (RE), arable land (AL), social insurance (SI), and unemployment (UE) to GDP variance increase, while the contribution from GDP itself decreases. By Period 10, the external variables have made substantial contributions to GDP variance. Specifically, CO₂ emissions and unemployment each account for approximately 10–20% of the variance, whereas renewable energy, arable land, and social insurance each contribute about 20–30%. This variance decomposition (VD) analysis provides insights into the dynamic interactions and relative significance of each variable in explaining GDP fluctuations over time.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study reveals that carbon emissions and arable land positively influence Pakistan's economic growth, while insufficient renewable energy, inadequate social insurance, and high unemployment rates hinder it. The robust least squares regression, ECM, and ARDL analyses all support these findings. The Impulse Response Function (IRF) and Variance Decomposition Analysis (VDA) suggest that renewable energy consumption and social insurance will significantly affect economic growth over the next decade, with potential adverse impacts from high unemployment. These insights provide valuable direction for policymakers to improve economic development through better management of natural resources, enhanced social policies, and increased renewable energy use.

The empirical findings of this study underscore several key policy recommendations to enhance Pakistan's economic growth and sustainability. The analysis indicates that while carbon emissions and arable land contribute positively to economic growth, inadequate renewable energy consumption, social insurance, and high unemployment levels present significant challenges. To address these issues, it is crucial for the government to promote the sustainable use of natural resources through awareness programs. Such initiatives can reduce reliance on fossil fuel imports and encourage the use of domestic resources. Reforms in the education sector should focus on raising environmental sustainability awareness, and there is a need to modernize outdated technologies to minimize resource consumption. Given the rapid urbanization in Pakistan, regulating urban expansion to mitigate environmental pollution is also essential. Additionally, reforestation efforts could play a significant role in reducing carbon emissions. On the policy front, establishing robust insurance programs to protect farmers from income losses due to currency fluctuations is recommended. Strengthening social safety nets, such as cash transfer programs, food subsidies, and targeted aid, will help households vulnerable to GDP fluctuations. Companies should also consider using financial tools like futures contracts and options to hedge against exchange rate risks. To mitigate the impact of energy prices and agricultural spending, incentives for adopting renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind power, should be provided. This shift can reduce dependency on fossil fuels and stabilize energy costs. Moreover, investing in value chains and agribusiness projects rather than solely focusing on crop

production could enhance the value added to agriculture, create jobs, and stimulate economic growth.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

Funding

The study has not received any external funding.

Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

REFERENCES AND NOTES

1. Abbasi, K. R., Shahbaz, M., Jiao, Z., & Tufail, M. (2021). How energy consumption, industrial growth, urbanization, and CO2 emissions affect economic growth in Pakistan? A novel dynamic ARDL simulations approach. *Energy*, 221, 119793.
2. Adebayo, T. S., Alola, A. A., Ullah, S., & Abbas, S. (2023). The growth impacts of agriculture value-added, energy utilization, and environmental degradation in Pakistan: Causality in continuous wavelet transform approach. *Natural Resources Forum*. Oxford, UK: Blackwell Publishing Ltd.
3. Amin, M. M. I., & Rahman, M. M. (2024). Assessing effects of agriculture value added industry value added and imports value added percentage to GDP on CO2 emissions in Bangladesh: An ARDL and NARDL approach. Online available at: <https://eartharxiv.org/repository/view/6901/> (accessed on 10th June, 2024).
4. Ashfaq, S., Liangrong, S., Waqas, F., Gulzar, S., Mujtaba, G., & Nasir, R. M. (2024). Renewable energy and green economic growth nexus: Insights from simulated dynamic ARDL. *Gondwana Research*, 127, 288-300.
5. Atif, M., Khan, A. A., Ahmed, S., & Yaqoob, M. (2024). Socio-economic inclusion and sustainable economic growth: Evidence from Pakistan. *Bulletin of Business and Economics (BBE)*, 13(1).
6. Bölük, G., & Mert, M. (2015). The renewable energy, growth and environmental Kuznets curve in Turkey: An ARDL approach. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 52, 587-595.
7. Busu, M. (2020). Analyzing the impact of the renewable energy sources on economic growth at the EU level using an ARDL model. *Mathematics*, 8(8), 1367.
8. Danish, & Hassan, S. T. (2023). Investigating the interaction effect of urbanization and natural resources on environmental sustainability in Pakistan. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, 20(8), 8477-8484.
9. Gyimah, J., Hayford, I. S., Nwigwe, U. A., & Opoku, E. O. (2023). The role of energy and economic growth towards sustainable environment through carbon emissions mitigation. *PLOS Climate*, 2(3), e0000116.
10. Habiba, U., Xinbang, C., & Ali, S. (2023). Investigating the impact of financial development on carbon emissions: Does the use of renewable energy and green technology really contribute to achieving low-carbon economies? *Gondwana Research*, 121, 472-485.
11. Iorember, P. T., Yusoff, N. Y. M., Abachi, P. T., Usman, O., & Alola, A. A. (2024). Effect of exchange rate uncertainty, energy prices and sectoral spending on agriculture value added, household consumption, and domestic investment. *Heliyon*, 10(9), e30138.
12. Khan, I., Muhammad, I., Sharif, A., Khan, I., & Ji, X. (2024). *IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 4(1), 154-166 (2024)
- Unlocking the potential of renewable energy and natural resources for sustainable economic growth and carbon neutrality: A novel panel quantile regression approach. *Renewable Energy*, 221, 119779.
13. Khan, I., Xue, J., Zaman, S., & Mehmood, Z. (2023). Nexus between FDI, economic growth, industrialization, and employment opportunities: Empirical evidence from Pakistan. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 14(3), 3153-3175.
14. Khan, S., Raza, M., Ali, L., Ali, Y., & Ali, M. (2024). Tourism development and economic growth in Pakistan: A theoretical analysis. *International Journal of Contemporary Issues in Social Sciences*, 3(1), 225-232.
15. Khaskheli, M. B., Wang, S., Yan, X., & He, Y. (2023). Innovation of the social security, legal risks, sustainable management practices and employee environmental awareness in the China–Pakistan economic corridor. *Sustainability*, 15(2), 1021.
16. Njenga, J. K. (2024). Electricity consumption and economic growth in Kenya: An ARDL bound test approach. *Journal of Energy Research and Reviews*, 16(1), 28-36.
17. Pachiyappan, D., Ansari, Y., Alam, M. S., Thoudam, P., Alagirisamy, K., & Manigandan, P. (2021). Short and long-run causal effects of CO2 emissions, energy use, GDP and population growth: Evidence from India using the ARDL and VECM approaches. *Energies*, 14(24), 8333.
18. Raihan, A. (2023). The dynamic nexus between economic growth, renewable energy use, urbanization, industrialization, tourism, agricultural productivity, forest area, and carbon dioxide emissions in the Philippines. *Energy Nexus*, 9, 100180.
19. Raza, M. Y., Wu, R., & Lin, B. (2023). A decoupling process of Pakistan's agriculture sector: Insights from energy and economic perspectives. *Energy*, 263, 125658.
20. Raza, M. Y., & Tang, S. (2024). Nuclear energy, economic growth and CO2 emissions in Pakistan: Evidence from extended STRIPAT model. *Nuclear Engineering and Technology*.
21. Shah, Z., Zaman, K., Khan, H. U. R., & Rashid, A. (2022). The economic value of natural resources and its implications for Pakistan's economic growth. *Commodities*, 1(2), 65-97.
22. Shinwari, R., Zakeria, I., Usman, M., & Sadiq, M. (2024). Revisiting the relationship between FDI, natural resources, and economic growth in Afghanistan: Does political (in) stability matter? *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 15, 5174-5203.
23. Siddik, A. B., Khan, S., Khan, U., Yong, L., & Murshed, M. (2023). The role of renewable energy finance in achieving low-carbon growth: Contextual evidence from leading renewable energy-investing countries. *Energy*, 270, 126864.
24. Singh, S., Sharma, G. D., Radulescu, M., Balsalobre-Lorente, D., & Bansal, P. (2023). Do natural resources impact economic growth: An investigation of P5+1 countries under sustainable management. *Geoscience Frontiers*, 101595.
25. Sikder, M., Wang, C., Rahman, M. M., Yeboah, F. K., Alola, A.

- A., & Wood, J. (2024). Green logistics and circular economy in alleviating CO2 emissions: Does waste generation and GDP growth matter in EU countries? *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 449, 141708.
26. Sulaiman, C., & Abdul-Rahim, A. S. (2018). Population growth and CO2 emission in Nigeria: A recursive ARDL approach. *Sage Open*, 8(2), 2158244018765916.
27. Wang, F., Wong, W. K., Ortiz, G. G. R., Al Shraah, A., Mabrouk, F., Li, J., & Li, Z. (2023). Economic analysis of sustainable exports value addition through natural resource management and artificial intelligence. *Resources Policy*, 82, 103541.
28. Wang, J., & Azam, W. (2024). Natural resource scarcity, fossil fuel energy consumption, and total greenhouse gas emissions in top emitting countries. *Geoscience Frontiers*, 15(2), 101757.
29. Zafar, M. R., Farooq, A., & Ali, M. H. (2024). Operational necessity: Harnessing state-owned enterprises privatization for economic and governance reform in Pakistan. *Journal of Humanities, Health and Social Sciences*, 2(1), 1-14.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of Sherwan Journals and/or the editor(s). Sherwan Journals and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.